

MESO-MACRO MECHENICAL BEHAVIOUR OF DRY FIBER FABRICS

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SUMMARY: Fibre fabrics are among the most efficient reinforcements for thin composites, and are increasingly used, especially in the field of transportation. They allow to achieve complex shapes in a single operation by forming a fabric on a given surface. The knowledge and modelling of dry fabric behaviour is necessary for these manufacturing. Firstly, a biaxial tensile device will be presented. To show essential proprieties of fabric behaviour, strain ratio and angular orientation between the two direction of weaving are adjustable. Tests, carried out on several fabrics, show that mechanical behaviour of fabrics is a multiscale problem, non linear and biaxial. Models, describing an elementary mesh, are then identified. It is shown that local phenomena (such as undulation variation and yarn flattening) mainly influence global behaviour. 3D simulations of the elementary mesh are performed to analyse them. The whole results are used to build specific finite elements made of woven cells.

KEYWORDS: Dry fiber fabrics, Meso-macro properties, Biaxial tensile test, Modelling of fabric behaviour, 3D Simulations, Forming simulation.

INTRODUCTION

Use of fibre fabrics is increasing especially in automotive and aerospace industry as thin composites reinforcement. Among the various manufacturing process available, some of them like R.T.M. (Resin Transfer Moulding) [1] or draping operations [2] use mechanical properties of the fabric, in particular their capability to be deformed. So they will be more precisely concerned by this study. The design of composite parts by such methods is quite difficult because its feasibility depends on the orientation of yarns and on the mechanical behaviour of the fabric during the forming process. Problems able to occur during this operation concern yarns breaking (due to excessive tensile load) or buckling (due to great compressive load) and folds appearance (when angular variations between yarns are too large). Those defects are limits of the deformation and tensile state in fabric during the forming process. The manufacturing tools are costly, so, to have a simulation tool able to tell about the feasibility of a composite part and to give the right adjustments to the manufacturing parameters could be a real advantage. The aim of this work is to reach to a finite element simulation tool specific to forming process of fabrics. It is then necessary to well know the mechanical behaviour of fabrics.

BIAXIAL TENSILE TESTS AND MODELLING

Fabrics behaviour

Studies on woven composites are numerous [3] (for instance). Usually, they aim at defining the characteristics of an homogeneous equivalent material and forecasting the matrix damage. The problem for dry fabrics is quite different because the absence of resin allows a great freedom of displacement to the yarns which mainly influences the fabric global behaviour. Studies on fabrics are fewer [4].

The main characteristics of a fabric, resulting from the absence of resin and yarn type constituents, are [5]:

an absence of compressive and bending stiffness;

an absence of sliding between warp and weft thread: a square pattern drawn prior to forming, alternatively on warp and weft yarn, become curved after deformation but remain continuous. The fabric can then be considered as a continuous 3D surface (Fig. 1).

an absence of in plane shear stiffness. As a consequence, great angular variations are allowed between warp and weft directions and constitute the main deformation mode (values up to 60° are possible in some cases).

a multiscale non linear behaviour that will be detailed further.

Fig. 1: Deformation of a glass fibre fabric[6]. Fig. 2: Biaxial tests on a carbon twill weave.

Three observation levels can be distinguished. The first and immediate scale is the one of the fabric called macroscopic. The structural computations and especially the forming simulations (which are our goal) are made at this level. Then comes the scale of the elementary pattern of weaving called mesoscopic because intermediary considering the third scale (microscopic). The last one deals with the numerous fibres constituting the yarn. Tests on fabric in a yarn direction classically show a progressive hardening area before a linear zone (Fig. 2) even if the yarn has a linear tensile behaviour. This non linear area is a significant part of the global behaviour. This macroscopic behaviour type non linearity is a translation of phenomena occurring at both lower scales. Indeed, at mesoscopic scale there are variations of the natural undulation (because of weaving) of the fabric: when solicited the yarns tends to straighten (Fig. 3). This is a geometric type non linearity which is complemented and amplified by others at microscopic scale. Under compressive load at the contact point between the two

directions, there is a rearrangement of fibres that modifies the cross section of each thread and mainly influences the global behaviour.

Fig. 3: Undulations variations.

Fig. 4: Biaxial tensile device and specimen.

Biaxial tests

The purpose of such a device is to show and quantify the effects of microscopic and mesoscopic non linearity on global macroscopic behaviour. It also was developed in order to establish relations between the two tension loads and the two strains.

The device [7] is based on the principle of two articulated lozenges (Fig. 4). When it is submitted to a compressive load it generates tensile deformation in each direction of the cross shaped specimen put in the middle of the contrivance. The strain ratio and the angle between the two direction of tension are adjustable. The second parameter will allow to represent the behaviour of fabrics in real cases, knowing that angular variations are significant during the forming process and constitute the main mode of deformation.

The cross shape is particularly adapted to such tests for fabrics because of the absence of in-plane shear stiffness. Consequently, it insures an homogenous strain field on the woven central part.

Captors put within the specimen allow to get curves of load versus strain in each tension direction. Figure 2 presents the results for a 2x2 twill weave of carbon fibres. It underscores the non linear aspect of the behaviour whereas the constitutive yarn has a linear response to a tensile load. A second major property is demonstrated: this non linear behaviour is a biaxial characteristic. Indeed, what occurs in one direction is strongly related to the strain ratio, i.e. to what appends in the other direction. In particular, the maximum of non linearity is obtained when the other direction is free; then the solicited yarns become totally straight (as shown Fig. 3).

Model for plain weave fabric

Models able to relate both loads to both strain in the fabric are identified from the previous experimental results. The first one is a model in which threads are represented by their mean line themselves schematized by portions of straight yarns (Fig. 5) [8]. The study of elementary mesh equilibrium and geometric relations between the various quantities leads to a non linear system of equations (Fig. 5) solved by a dichotomy or a pseudo Newton's method according to whether strains or deformations are set.

Fig. 5: Model of straight yarn. Representation and system to be solved.

This model suits quite well to most of fabrics used in forming process for composites (Fig. 6). Moreover, although it is established for a plain weave fabric, it can efficiently be used for other pattern like a 2x2 twill weave (Fig. 1).

Fig. 6: Comparison experiment/model for a very unbalanced taffeta of glass fibres.

One limit of this model lies in the fact that yarns can not be represented entirely (that means correctly in 3 dimensions). So a more realistic model is developed to take into account the whole geometry, including cross section shape. In this model the yarn still be represented by its mean line but this last is schematized by curved portions (Fig. 7) [9]. Considering also each specific characteristic of fabric behaviour, this last model is in good agreement with experimental results for every tested woven structures.

Fig. 7: Curved yarn model.

NUMERICAL SIMULATIONS AT MESO AND MACRO SCALE

3D simulation of elementary pattern

Local information are difficult to obtained experimentally. The 3D simulations at mesh scale have two aims. First, it goals at analysing the micro and meso non linear phenomena influencing global behaviour. Moreover, it can allow to define the characteristics of a fabric prior to design, from its components and weaving.

Because of the nature of the yarn, made of many fibres, and the resulting lack of most stiffness, the problem is not classic. Calculations are carried out in the field of great deformations. The chosen law is hypoelastic type. In order to take into account the absence of some stiffnesses (in bending, shear and compression), it was shown that shear moduli and Poisson's ratios must be equal to zero, and that transverse tensile moduli are negligible front of tensile modulus in the yarn direction [10]. But nil or nearly nil values of some mechanical coefficients leads to numerical difficulties when used in simulations. This is a phenomenon similar to the hourglass modes problems encountered in the building of reduced-integration elements. Those modes are, here, controlled by adding artificial stiffness that doesn't influences the solution [11]. Otherwise, Young's moduli in transverse direction being very different of the one in yarn direction, directions of anisotropy have to remain strictly in material directions (the ones of yarns). This condition is fulfilled thanks to reinforcements fixed to the elements in the yarn direction.

The longitudinal modulus is identified from a tensile test on a yarn. The transverse modulus is given by the crushing law:

$$E_3 = E_0 \left| \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_{33}^n \right| \left| \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_{11}^m \right| \quad (6)$$

where E_0 , m et n are three material parameters, ϵ_{33} and ϵ_{11} are the transverse and longitudinal strains, respectively.

Since it is difficult to perform a compression test on a yarn, this crushing law is identified with a biaxial test $k=1$, using an inverse method. The principle is to build a least square error function which quantify the difference between the experimental curve and the finite element curve (for given parameters). This function is minimised with the Levenberg-Marquardt method [12][13] to optimise the parameters.

Simulations carried out on a plain weave fabric made of glass fibres (Fig. 8) show a good agreement with experiments (Fig. 9). Two local phenomena can be observed:

- important undulation changes (Fig. 10),
- a crucial role played by the transverse compressive behaviour: the yarn flattening can reach values up to 40% (Fig. 11).

Fig. 8: Plain weave mesh.

Fig. 9: Comparison tests (solid lines)/simulations.

Fig. 10: Undulation changes for a biaxial test where the warp direction is free.

Fig. 11: Transverse strain for a biaxial test $k=1$.

It is then possible to see the influence of some geometrical and mechanical parameters. For example, the comparison of several elementary patterns (plain weave, twill 2x2 and twill 3x1, Fig. 12) shows that the plain weave has the behaviour the most non linear: more the undulation of the fabric is important, more the behaviour is non linear.

Fig. 12: Comparison of the behaviour of plain weave, twill 2x2 and twill 3x1, for $k=1$.

Simulation of fibre fabric forming

Problems able to occur while fabric forming (for example by stamping in the first step of R.T.M. process) are linked to deformation and tension state in preform during the transformation. In particular, there is two limit criteria defining the feasibility of the part. The first and main one concerns appearance of folds when angular variations are to large to be supported by the fabric. The second one is related to high tensile load in yarns that leads to yarns breaking.

The goal of this simulation tool is to predict the feasibility of a non developable surface for given fabric and manufacturing tools, before making those last. Other important results, such as the reinforcements directions after shaping or the right adjustments for tools and process parameters, can be deduced from the simulation of fabric forming.

Fig. 13: Finite element of woven cells.

Finite elements made of elementary woven cells are built (Fig. 13), accounting for various characteristics mentioned in the previous paragraphs [14]. This approach is justified by the non sliding hypothesis already proved. A Newton's incremental scheme is used to solve the non linear problem set down by the Lagrangian equilibrium (Eqn. 7).

$$\sum_{p=1}^{n \text{ cell}} {}^p D_{\mathbf{u}}(\mathbf{E})\boldsymbol{\eta} : {}^p \mathbf{W} - \int_{\Omega_0} \mathbf{f}_0 \cdot \boldsymbol{\eta} dV_0 - \int_{\Gamma_{t_0}} \mathbf{t}_0 \cdot \boldsymbol{\eta} dA_0 = 0 \quad (7)$$

\mathbf{E} is strain tensor of Green-Lagrange, ncell number of meshes, \mathbf{t}_0 , \mathbf{f}_0 external efforts and ${}^p \mathbf{W}$ a static lagrangian tensor for the p-mesh such as:

$${}^p \mathbf{W} = {}^p T^{11} {}^p L_{0_1} {}^p \mathbf{h}_{10} \otimes {}^p \mathbf{h}_{10} + {}^p T^{22} {}^p L_{0_2} {}^p \mathbf{h}_{20} \otimes {}^p \mathbf{h}_{20} \quad (8)$$

For simplicity reason, the presentation will be restricted to a four node element with its direction directed along the material directions (which is possible in most of cases). Nevertheless a triangular element is built in the same way and elements which directions are not these of the cells can be obtained.

After a classic bilinear nodal interpolation, the calculations are reduced to operations on only four cells, by analogy with Gauss's reduction. Then, stiffness matrices and internal load vector can be explicitly expressed according to terms of the nodal interpolation matrix, number of cells on the element, characteristic length of the cell, mechanical behaviour evaluated from the biaxial tests and represented thanks to models previously evoked, and tensions in the yarns (Eqn. 9 to 11).

$$(\mathbf{F}_{\text{int}}^e)_s = \sum_{i=1}^2 \sum_{j=1}^2 \frac{N_C N_T}{4} \left(\bar{B}_{11s} L_{0_1} T^{11} \|\mathbf{g}_{10}\|^{-2} + \bar{B}_{22s} L_{0_2} T^{22} \|\mathbf{g}_{20}\|^{-2} \right) \quad (9)$$

$$\left(\mathbf{K}_{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}^e \right)_{rs} = \sum_{i=1}^2 \sum_{j=1}^2 \frac{N_C N_T}{4} \left(L_{0_1} T^{11} \frac{1}{\|\mathbf{g}_{10}\|^2} \frac{\partial N^k}{\partial \xi_1} \frac{\partial N^q}{\partial \xi_1} + L_{0_2} T^{22} \frac{1}{\|\mathbf{g}_{20}\|^2} \frac{\partial N^k}{\partial \xi_2} \frac{\partial N^q}{\partial \xi_2} \right) \quad (10)$$

$$\left(\mathbf{K}^e \right)_{rs} = \sum_{i=1}^2 \sum_{j=1}^2 \frac{N_C N_T}{4} \left(\bar{B}_{\alpha\alpha r} \left(\frac{L_{0\alpha}}{\|\mathbf{g}_{\alpha 0}\|^2 \|\mathbf{g}_{\beta 0}\|^2} \frac{\partial T^{\alpha\alpha}}{\partial E^{\beta\beta}} \right) \bar{B}_{\beta\beta s} \right) \quad (11)$$

Fig. 14: Stamping by ellipsoidal punch. Influence of undulations variations.

Considering that only the effectively present stiffness in the fabric are calculated, numerical efficiency is high. It takes few time to get the results, that is the displacements of each node and the tension in every yarns. The first data leads to the strain and deformation of the fabric,

but also to angles between weaving directions. Then, it is possible to give the reinforcements directions after shaping process and evaluate if some folds are able to appear or not. The second result allows to predict yarns breaking and to adjust parameters like pressure on die cushions.

The simulations results are in good agreement with stamping experiment [6]. Figure 14 shows the influence of the undulations variations. They have to be taken into account to deal with reality. On the figure it doesn't seem to have a great importance because the fabric tested is rather flat (used in R.T.M. process). The differences would be largely greater with on other more undulated fabric or even more with knitted type materials which allow high deformations [15].

CONCLUSIONS

Various observations made on fabric classically used in industrial fields as composites reinforcements allowed to define specific properties of dry fabrics behaviour. A biaxial tensile device was especially designed to test simultaneously warp and weft yarns. It led to both quantitative and qualitative results which were used to establish and identify behaviour models. In particular, it allowed to conclude on the biaxial and non linear character of the mechanical behaviour. Transverse behaviour proving to be very important, a 3D simulation of elementary mesh was carried out to analyse more precisely mesoscopic phenomena such as yarns flattening and undulations variations. At last, the whole results were used to build specific finite elements made of woven unit cells. Forming process simulations using those elements proved to have a high numerical efficiency.

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